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A new species of silverfish of the genus *Persiatelurina* Molero, Tahami, Gaju et Sadeghi, 2018 (Zygentoma: Nicoletiidae) from Stavropol Region of Russia

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Abstract. A new silverfish species *Persiatelurina zabaluevi* sp. n. is described from the Mashuk forest park in Pyatigorsk (Stavropol Region of Russia). It differs from other species of this genus by the structure of maxilla, apical palpomeres of maxillary and labial palps, hind margin of thoracic tergites and urotergite X, urosternite VII, urocoxites VIII and IX, number divisions of female ovipositor. The new species has an elongated last palpomere of the labial palps, relatively long and narrow tibiae of the fore and middle legs, and a deep concave on the posterior base of urotergite X. Ratio of length to width of apical palpomere of female labial palps is 1.5–1.6, tibia I – 3.8, tibia II – 4.3, depth to width of concave on the hind margin of urotergite X is about 0.75.

Key words: Nicoletiidae, Atelurinae, *Persiatelurina*, new species, key to species.

Новый вид щетинохвосток рода *Persiatelurina* Molero, Tahami, Gaju et Sadeghi, 2018 (Zygentoma: Nicoletiidae) из Ставропольского края России

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Резюме. Описан новый вид щетинохвосток *Persiatelurina zabaluevi* sp. n. из Машукского лесопарка Пятигорска (Ставропольский край, Россия). Он отличается от других видов этого рода строением нижней челюсти, апикальных члеников нижнечелюстного и нижнегубного щупиков, заднего края грудных тергитов и брюшного тергита X, числом члеников яйцевода самки. У нового вида удлинённый последний членик нижнегубных щупиков, сравнительно длинные и узкие голени передних и средних ног, глубокая выемка заднего основания 10-го тергита брюшка. Отношение длины к ширине апикального членика нижнегубных щупиков самки 1.5–1.6, передней голени 3.8, средней голени 4.3, глубины выемки заднего основания уротергита X к её ширине около 0.75.

Ключевые слова: Nicoletiidae, Atelurinae, *Persiatelurina*, новый вид, определительная таблица.

Silverfish of the family Nicoletiidae are eyeless and lack pigment [Smith, McRae, 2016]. Nicoletiid fauna is very diverse, including six subfamilies and about 90 genera [Mendes, 1994]; among them about 70 genera and more than 140 species belong to the subfamily Atelurinae [Mendes, 2012]. They are found in soil-related and subterranean habitats in regions with warm temperate, subtropical and tropical climatic conditions. The genus *Persiatelurina* Molero, Tahami, Gaju et Sadeghi, 2018 with the type species *P. farsiana* Molero, Tahami, Gaju et Sadeghi, 2018 was described from Fars Province of Iran [Tahami et al., 2018] and currently includes five valid species. In addition to the Iranian type species of the genus, one congener, i.e. *P. caucasica* (Kaplin, 2016), is known from Abkhazia and another two from Russia: *P. daghestaniana* Kaplin, 2021 from Dagestan and *P. crimeana* Kaplin, 2024 from the Karadag Nature Reserve (Crimea) [Kaplin, 2016; Kaplin, Vasin, 2019; Kaplin, Martynov, 2024]. Species of the genus *Persiatelurina* are characterized by the presence of three pairs of styli on urosternites VII–IX, 1 + 1 exertile vesicles on urosternite II, and 1 + 1 pseudovesicles on urosternite VII; the galea with two apical conules and pretarsi with small pulvilli. Below we describe a new species of the genus, namely *P. zabaluevi* Kaplin, sp. n.,

based on specimens from the North Caucasus (Stavropol Region, Pyatigorsk environs, Mashuk forest park, foothills of the Greater Caucasus).

Three specimens of females, which were collected in the Mashuk forest park near Pyatigorsk were stored in 75% ethanol. The specimens, i.e., holotype and two paratypes (females) were dissected and mounted on glass microscope slides in the Berlese fluid. Figures were made using microscope and drawing tool. The types of the new species are deposited in the collection of the All-Russian Institute of Plant Protection (VIZR, St Petersburg, Pushkin, Russia).

Order Zygentoma Börner, 1904
Family Nicoletiidae Escherich, 1905
Subfamily Atelurinae Remington, 1954
Genus *Persiatelurina* Molero, Tahami,
Gaju et Sadeghi, 2018
Persiatelurina zabaluevi Kaplin, sp. n.
(Figs 1–13)

Material. Holotype, ♀ (slides) (VIZR): “Russia, Stavropol Region, Mashuk, forest park, near the Lake Proval, in the forest litter, I.A. Zabaluev, 21.IV.2021, with ants *Tetramorium* sp., 44°02'48"N, 43°05'56"E”. Paratypes: 2♀ (slides) (VIZR), the same data and locality as in the holotype.

Figs 1–13. *Persiatelurina zabaluevi* sp. n., female, details of structure.

1 – scapus, pedicel and flagellomere of antenna; 2 – maxillary palp and maxilla; 3 – labial palp with labium (part); 4 – metanotum; 5 – hind leg (tarsus, tibia, femur, trochanter and coxa); 6 – lyriform spine; 7 – urosternite II; 8 – urotergite X; 9 – urosternite VII with stylus and subgenital plate; 10 – urocoxite VIII with stylus; 11 – urocoxite IX with stylus; 12 – gonapophysis VIII; 13 – gonapophysis IX. 1–11 – holotype; 12–13 – paratype. Scale bars 0.1 mm.

Рис. 1–13. *Persiatelurina zabaluevi* sp. n., самка, детали строения.

1 – основной членик, ножка и членики жгутика усика; 2 – нижнечелюстной щупик и нижняя челюсть; 3 – нижнегубной щупик и нижняя губа (часть); 4 – заднегрудной тергит; 5 – задняя нога (лапка, голень, бедро, вертлуг и тазик); 6 – лировидная щетинка; 7 – стернит второго сегмента брюшка; 8 – тергит X сегмента брюшка; 9 – стернит VII сегмента брюшка с грифельком и субгенитальной пластинкой; 10 – коксит VIII сегмента брюшка с грифельком; 11 – коксит IX сегмента брюшка с грифельком; 12 – передний гонапофиз яйцеклада; 13 – задний гонапофиз яйцеклада. 1–11 – голотип; 12–13 – паратип. Масштабные линейки 0.1 мм.

Description. Body length 3–4.5 mm; head length 0.17–0.28 mm; thorax length 1.18–1.78 mm, abdomen length 1.58–2.45 mm. Head width 0.62–0.78 mm; thorax width 1.17–1.28 mm; abdominal segment IX width about 0.55–0.72 mm. General body colour whitish with golden setae and scales. Small size, elongate ateluriform shape, covered with relatively large scales, including head and coxae. Body 2.5–2.7 times longer than wide; head small, about 2.6–2.8 times wider than long. Articles of cerci and caudal filament only with 1, 2 or 3 dorsal, ventral and lateral simple trichobothria. Scapus and pedicel of antenna without trichobothria, with simple and apical bifurcation macrosetae. Flagellomere includes 12 or 13 articles. The first joint of antennal flagellomere with 5–7, the second one with 1–2, the 3–8th, 10th and 12th annuli with 1 simple trichobothrium. All articles of flagellomere also with 2 rows of simple macrosetae (Fig. 1). Mandibles with well-developed incisor and molar regions and with 8–10 simple macrosetae along outer

surface. Incisor region with 8 incisive teeth. Maxillary palps with 5 palpomeres. Ultimate palpomere of maxillary palps about 1.2–1.3 times longer than penultimate. Ultimate palpomere with 3 apical sensorial papillae of usual form (Fig. 2).

Galea of maxilla with 2 apical conules, one of which more rounded than the other. Upper surface of galea with about 15–20 setae. Apical tooth of lacinia single-top, pectinate protheca long with about 18 narrow hyaline projections; four inclined bifurcated and one large and perpendicular lamella in apical part with 5 lateral projections. Lacinia also with a row of 5 or 6 simple macrosetae and 2 more small setae on under surface of the lacinia basal part (Fig. 2).

Apical palpomere of labial palp ovoid, in female about 1.5–1.6 times longer than wide, with 6 typical sensorial papillae (Fig. 3). Under surface of last three palpomeres of labial palps with numerous relatively shortened and thickened, slightly curved,

apically bifurcated setae. Glossae divided into two pairs of lobes, shorter than paraglossae. Paraglossae and glossae with simple setae.

Lateral margins of thoracic tergites with a row of setae, two of which in the posterior corners are the longest, without sensory fields. Anterior border of pronotum with numerous small setae. Posterior margin of pro-, meso- and metanotum with 8–9, 7 and 5–6 thin setae, respectively (Fig. 4).

Legs quite elongate. The tarsi of all legs are four-segmented. Coxae and femora widened (Fig. 5). Ratio length to width of femora I, II and III about 1.88, 1.76 and 1.8; tibia – 3.75, 4.32 and 4.46, respectively. Apex of dorsal part of tibia I, II and III with 2, femur with 1 lyriform spine (Fig. 6). Tibia also with 1 relatively large apical spur and 4 ventral simple macrochaetae. Middle part of femur I, II and III with 2 long simple macrochaetae. Praetarsus with 2 strong claws, 2 small pulvilli, medial empodial claw and slightly convex small support oval platform with 3–4 transverse ribs.

Urotergites I–VIII infralaterally with 5 + 5 simple macrosetae; inner setae more robust and longer than others. Posterior

margin of urotergites I–VIII with 4–6 setulae. Urotergite IX with posterolateral corners protruding, with 2 + 2 apical, 4–5 + 4–5 outer and 1–2 + 1–2 inner shorter macrosetae. Urotergite X with semi-circular concave hind margin. Ratio depth to width of concave about 0.75. Apex of posterolateral angles of urotergite X with 1 + 1 long and strong macrosetae, inner margin of notch with 4 + 4 macrosetae (Fig. 8).

Urosternite I with 1 + 1 submedian small setulae. Urosternite II with one pair of submedian vesicles (Fig. 7). Urosternite III–VI with 4–6 + 4–6 setae in the hind margin. Urosternite VII with one pair of pseudovesicles and with subgenital plate (Fig. 9). Subgenital plate well-developed, 1.7 times wider than long, with rounded hind margin and with single row of simple setae, apically slightly acute. Styli on urosternites VII–IX. Length ratios of styli (without apical spines) and urosternite VII about 0.64, urocoxites VIII – 0.75, urocoxites IX – 0.85, apical spines and styli – 0.25, 0.22 and 0.14, respectively (Figs 9–11).

Ovipositor spindle-shaped, slightly shorter than styli IX, gonapophyses VIII and IX with 9 divisions and acute apices. Gonapophyses VIII with numerous outer straight setae. Outer

Table 1. Main morphological differences between *Persiatelurina zabaluevi* sp. n., *P. daghestaniana*, *P. caucasica* and *P. crimeana* [Kaplin, 2016; Kaplin, Vasin, 2019; Kaplin, Martynov, 2024].

Таблица 1. Основные морфологические различия между *Persiatelurina zabaluevi* sp. n., *P. daghestaniana*, *P. caucasica* и *P. crimeana* [Kaplin, 2016; Kaplin, Vasin, 2019; Kaplin, Martynov, 2024].

Morphological characters Морфологические особенности	<i>P. daghestaniana</i>	<i>P. caucasica</i>	<i>P. crimeana</i>	<i>P. zabaluevi</i> sp. n.
Body length, mm Длина тела, мм	3.2–3.8	4.1–4.6	3.2–3.8	3–4.5
Number of macrochaetae on the inner margin of lacinia Число макрохет на внутреннем крае лацинии нижней челюсти	5	7–8	5	5–6
Ratio of lengths of ultimate to penultimate palpomeres of maxillary palps / Отношение длин вершинного и предвершинного члеников нижнечелюстных щупиков	1.2	1.3	1.2	1.2–1.3
Number of apical sensorial papillae on the ultimate palpomere of maxillary palps / Число апикальных сенсорных папилл на вершинном членике нижнечелюстных щупиков	4	3	3	3
Ratio on length to width of apical palpomere of female labial palps / Отношение длины к ширине апикального членика нижнегубных щупиков самки	1.4–1.5	1.5	1.3–1.4	1.5–1.6
Ratio length to width of tibia I Отношение длины к ширине передней голени	3.7	2.9	3.6	3.8
Ratio length to width of tibia II Отношение длины к ширине средней голени	4.2	2.6–2.7	3.4	4.3
Ratio length to width of tibia III Отношение длины к ширине задней голени	4.5	3.2	4	4.4
Number of setulae on the posterior margin of pronotum Число мелких щетинок на заднем основании переднеспинки	10	10–11	6–8	8–9
Ratio of lengths of styli (without apical spines) to urosternite VII / Отношение длин грифельков (без апикальных опорных игл) и уростернита VII	0.74	0.63	0.58	0.64
Ratio of lengths of styli (without apical spines) to urocoxite VIII / Отношение длин грифельков (без апикальных опорных игл) и урококситы VIII	0.78	0.63–0.66	0.7	0.75
Ratio of lengths of styli (without apical spines) to urocoxites IX / Отношение длин грифельков (без апикальных опорных игл) и урококситов IX	0.84	0.88–0.89	0.8	0.85
Ratio depth to width of concave hind margin of urotergite X (female) / Отношение глубины к ширине выемки заднего основания уротергита X (самка)	0.45	0.27	0.53	0.75
Number divisions of ovipositor Число члеников яйцеклада	9	9	8	9

margin of gonapophysis IX with one long sensorial setae on 2nd to 9th and three such setae on apical division (Figs 12, 13). Apical part of gonapophyses IX also with well-developed oval sensorial field.

Comparative remarks. The main differences between species are given in Table 1 and in the key below.

Etymology. The name of the new species derives from the surname of the collector Ilya Zabaluev.

**A key to the species of the genus *Persiatelurina*
(females)**

- 1(2). Ratio depth to width of concave on the hind margin of urotergite X – 1.17. Number divisions of ovipositor 7 ..
..... *P. farsiana*
- 2(1). Ratio depth to width of concave on the hind margin of urotergite X less than 1. Number divisions of ovipositor 8–9.
- 3(4). Ultimate palpomere of maxillary palps with four apical sensorial papillae. Ratio depth to width of concave on the hind margin of urotergite X about 0.45
..... *P. daghestaniana*
- 4(3). Ultimate palpomere of maxillary palps with three apical sensorial papillae. Ratio depth to width of concave on the hind margin of urotergite X less or more than 0.45.
- 5(4). Ratio depth to width of concave on the hind margin of urotergite X about 0.27. Ratios of lengths of styli (without apical spines) to urosternite VII and to urocoxites VIII about 0.63–0.66 *P. caucasica*
- 6(5). Ratio depth to width of concave on the hind margin of urotergite X more than 0.5. Ratios of lengths of styli (without apical spines) to urosternite VII less and to urocoxites VIII more than 0.63–0.66.
- 7(6). Ratio depth to width of concave on the hind margin of urotergite X about 0.53. Ratios of lengths of styli (without apical spines) to urosternite VII 0.58 and to urocoxites VIII 0.7 *P. crimeana*

- 8(6). Ratio depth to width of concave on the hind margin of urotergite X more than 0.53. Ratios of lengths of styli (without apical spines) to urosternite VII and to urocoxites VIII more than 0.58 and 0.7, respectively.
- 9(8). Ratio depth to width of concave on the hind margin of urotergite X about 0.75. Ratios of lengths of styli (without apical spines) to urosternite VII and to urocoxites VIII 0.64 and 0.75, respectively
..... *P. zabaluevi* sp. n.

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